

EFFECTS OF INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN Ti β 21s / SCS-6 COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

The fibre/matrix interfacial strength is often considered to be of paramount importance in determining the mechanical properties of composites. In order to investigate the influence of interfacial strength on fatigue crack growth resistance in titanium metal matrix composites, specimens of a commercially available continuous fibre-reinforced Ti β 21s/SCS-6 composite were heat treated at both solution treatment and ageing temperatures. All specimens were then pre-notched and tested under cyclic loading in three point-bending.

For each heat treatment, the interfacial properties of the composite were determined using a continuous load-displacement fibre push-out technique. The interfacial properties of solution treated specimens were found to be similar to those of the as-processed material and there was little effect on either the mode, or rate of fatigue crack propagation in the composite. However the peak aged specimens had reduced fatigue crack growth resistance and failed in fewer cycles. There was also a large increase in both the interfacial debonding stress and frictional stress measured for the peak aged material. The implications of these observations for micromechanisms of crack growth resistance in fibre reinforced composites are discussed.

Key words: Ti/SiC composites, interfacial properties, fatigue crack growth , fibre push-out, MMCs

1. INTRODUCTION

For the past 20 years, there has been considerable interest in the field of continuous fibre-reinforced titanium / silicon carbide composites for aerospace applications. Some of these envisaged components will operate under conditions where fatigue endurance may be critical.

Continuous fibre-reinforced titanium / silicon carbide composites can offer excellent fatigue crack growth resistance if sufficient numbers of intact fibres bridge the crack in its wake. These composite systems are unusual in that dominant cracks are usually produced during fatigue loading [1-3]. Thus the opportunity to characterise this crack growth resistance by the use of a fracture mechanics approach becomes feasible. One major challenge is to model and predict the effect of bridging fibres on the effective crack tip stress intensity, ΔK_{eff} . Many models with a predictive capability have been proposed [4-7], but their experimental verification requires much work. One parameter often used in such models is the shear strength of the fibre/matrix interface. Therefore changes in the fibre/matrix interfacial properties would be expected to influence the crack growth resistance of these materials.

A technique for the measurement of interfacial properties in fibre reinforced composites is fibre push-out [8,9]. This has been used in conjunction with continuous load monitoring during the push-out operation by various researchers [9-11] and allows an evaluation of the maximum shear stress

during the fibre/matrix debonding process, and a frictional shear stress during the fibre sliding process. These values will depend on: (i) the chemical nature and thickness of fibre / matrix reaction layers; (ii) the residual stresses set up between the fibres and the matrix on cooling (due to differences in thermal expansion coefficient between the fibres and the matrix); (iii) any volume changes in the matrix caused by phase transformations and (iv) the type of fibre coating.

There are relatively few examples in the literature of controlled studies on titanium metal matrix composites where increased or decreased interfacial properties have been correlated with changes in toughness or fatigue crack growth resistance. Previous work [12] on the metastable β Ti-15-3 system suggests that catastrophic failure was promoted by peak ageing, but the interfacial characteristics of the material are still to be determined. This present study addresses the issue in a metastable β Ti β 21s system by performing a series of heat treatments on a commercially available Ti β 21s / SCS-6 composite and then characterising their interfacial properties and fatigue crack growth resistance.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composite considered in this work was a commercially available Ti β 21s / SCS-6 composite in 8-ply unidirectional lay-ups reinforced with a nominal fibre volume fraction of 35%. It was produced in the form of a 300 x 300 x 2 mm³ plate. Test pieces in the as-processed condition were either solution treated at 910°C or aged at 540°C. Heat treatments were performed by encapsulating the specimens in an inert atmosphere and were all terminated by air cooling to room temperature. Solution treatment times of 2 or 6 hours were employed, while a single ageing time of 8 hours was used. The ageing treatment at 540°C has been shown to produce peak ageing in monolithic Ti β 21s .

2.1 Metallography

Transverse sections were taken of the composites in each of the heat treatments, and polished down to 1 μ m on diamond cloths. The fibre/matrix reaction layers were measured using a Jeol 6300 scanning electron microscope operating at 25 kV, where an average of at least 10 measurements was taken in all cases.

2.2 Interfacial characterisation

In order for fibre push-out tests to be carried out, slices were cut perpendicular to the fibre direction and then polished on both sides to a 1 μ m diamond finish and to a slice thickness of between 270-370 μ m. The specimen slices were then placed on a support block so that one row of fibres was above a 200 μ m machined groove. A QM100 remote optical telescope with a video recording system was used to position a cylindrical drill bit of 100 μ m diameter above the fibre (of nominal diameter 140 μ m) prior to the indentation process and to continuously monitor the push-out test. An ESH Servo-Hydraulic testing machine equipped with a 1 kN load cell was used to perform the indentation test under a constant cross-head displacement of 50 μ min⁻¹. This allowed a continuous load cross-head displacement trace during the fibre push-out process to be obtained. The interfacial properties were characterised in terms of a maximum stress before fibre debonding and a maximum frictional shear stress during fibre sliding after the debonding process. At least 10 fibres were pushed out from each slice.

The debonding interfacial shear stress, τ_d was then calculated from

$$\tau_d = P_d / (\pi d_f L_f) \quad (1)$$

where P_d = load applied when the fibre was observed to move, d_f = diameter of fibre and L_f = length of fibre (thickness of specimen). The frictional shear stress, τ_f was calculated at the maximum load reached during the fibre sliding process from

$$\tau_f = P / (\pi d_f (L_f - u)) \quad (2)$$

where P is the instantaneous applied load and u is the instantaneous displacement of the fibre during the test. The thickness of the testpiece was measured after the testing using a scanning electron microscope and u was estimated directly from the cross-head displacement.

2.3 Fatigue crack growth

Fatigue testing was performed using single edge-notched specimens in three-point bending. The specimens were of nominal dimensions $4 \times 2 \times 75 \text{ mm}^3$. A 1 mm notch was cut perpendicular to the fibre direction with a diamond saw of $150 \mu\text{m}$ thickness to give an initial notch to depth ratio, a_0/W , equal to 0.25. Cracks were grown perpendicular to the direction of fibre reinforcement and parallel to the stacking direction of fibres within the mat. All tests were carried out at an initial applied stress intensity, $\Delta K = 17 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, a frequency of 10 Hz and at a stress ratio, $R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$ of 0.5 (where σ_{\min} , σ_{\max} are the minimum and maximum nominal stresses applied over the fatigue cycle respectively). An ESH servo-hydraulic testing machine with a 10 kN load cell was used for these tests, and a constant load range was maintained. The crack length was measured using a direct current potential difference technique which resolves the crack length vertically from the notch. One test was carried out on each of the heat treated conditions and two tests on the as-processed condition. Fracture surfaces of specimens after failure were examined using an Hitachi S4000 Field Emission Gun scanning electron microscope (FEG SEM) operating at 25 kV and at 45° tilt.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Microstructure

As a result of the solution treatments, the fibre /matrix reaction product thickness was observed to increase (see Table 1). Qualitatively, the solution treatments also appeared to increase the grain size of the matrix alloy, but the grain size of the as-processed material was highly variable and these preliminary observations require quantification. On ageing, fine scale alpha precipitation was observed in the matrix to give an approximate volume fraction of alpha precipitates of 50%.

3.2 Interfacial properties

It can be seen in Table 2 that both the interfacial debonding and frictional shear stresses measured for the as-processed condition and after solution heat treatment at 910°C are very similar, even though the fibre/matrix reaction layer has grown significantly. In contrast, the peak aged condition displays both increased interfacial debonding and frictional shear stresses.

A typical load-displacement trace obtained during fibre push-out is shown in Figure 1. The load can be seen to increase until the fibre debonds from the matrix, and at which point there is a sudden load drop. Thereafter the fibre slides out from the matrix, with the shape of the load-displacement curve dependent on the frictional properties of the matrix. The peak stress reached during the fibre sliding process was observed to be higher than that reached when the fibre debonds from the matrix for greater than 95% of all fibres tested.

3.3 Fatigue crack growth

Crack growth resistance curves are shown in Figures 2 and 3 where the crack increment per cycle, da/dN is plotted versus total crack depth (including the notch). For a constant applied cyclic load range, an increase in crack depth will increase the *nominal* applied stress intensity range from its initial level of $\Delta K = 17 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. However, as can be clearly seen in Figure 2, crack growth rates tend to decrease with increasing crack depth increment and this illustrates the powerful influence of intact bridging fibres in reducing the effective stress intensity range, ΔK_{eff} . All as-processed and solution treated specimens behave similarly, but the delicate balance between crack arrest ($da/dN \leq 10^{-8} \text{ mm/cycle}$) and catastrophic failure that can exist is demonstrated by Figure 2 and Table 3.

Figure 3 shows that the peak aged material exhibits significantly faster crack growth rates ($da/dN \geq 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm/cycle}$) than the as-processed material. Moreover, failure occurs in 87,900 cycles compared to a minimum of 1,760,900 cycles for the other conditions (see Table 3). The fracture surface can also be seen to be significantly different, as there is a much greater degree of off-axis

growth and fibre pull-out in the as-processed material than in the peak aged specimen (see Figures 4 (a-b)). Note that in the as-processed specimen, a significant part of the crack growth is actually at large angles away from the Mode I direction. Therefore there will be some error in the precise crack growth increments calculated from the potential difference technique, but it still provides a useful comparison between these materials.

4. DISCUSSION

During fibre push-out testing, the peak frictional stress was almost always observed to be higher than the peak debonding stress. This phenomena has been observed by other researchers [7] and has been attributed to wear during the fibre sliding process. It illustrates the difficulties inherent to the identification of an unique interfacial strength for debonded interfaces. Another important observation is the distribution of interfacial strengths from different fibres in the same specimen. In one case, although most of the results were normally distributed, there were a few fibres with very high interfacial strengths, and this may be important in situations where failure of individual fibres can effect the balance between crack arrest and catastrophic failure [13]. However, fibre push-out testing appears to be a quick and easy technique which produces reliable and repeatable results, see Table 2.

The measured interfacial strengths are of very similar magnitude in the as-processed condition and after solution treatment for 2 and 6 hours at 910°C, during which the fibre matrix reaction layer has grown from 0.79 µm to 1.3 µm, see Table 1. This rate of growth can be shown to be consistent with the kinetics of reaction layer growth derived from the same system by other researchers [14]. However this appears to have had little effect on the fatigue crack growth resistance. This observation is of note since it implies that such a variation in processing conditions will not be critical to fatigue crack growth resistance in these materials.

Both the interfacial debonding stress and the interfacial frictional stress are much increased with ageing. This increased interfacial strength is also consistent with the limited fibre pull-out and the reduced angle of off-axis growth in the peak aged material (see Figure 4 (a-b)) compared to the as-processed material. The fatigue crack growth resistance of the peak aged composite is also much reduced, see Figure 3 and Table 3. This reduction in crack growth resistance appears to be a result of the premature failure of fibres in the peak aged composite, (such fibre failure has been confirmed using acoustic emission techniques). These observations are consistent with increased load transfer onto the fibres due to the increased interfacial bonding promoted by the ageing treatment. By inference, such effects appear to be due to the large amount of alpha precipitated in the peak aged material.

The detailed interpretation of the influence of interfacial strength on fatigue crack growth resistance requires great care. In particular, the definition of whether crack arrest takes place for any given system and pre crack geometry, will be critically dependent upon the level of initial ΔK_{app} [13]. In all tests to date, if fibre failure does not occur, then crack arrest results. In the tests reported here, the delicate balance between crack arrest and eventual catastrophic failure is exemplified by the as-processed and solution treated conditions. Therefore, fibre failure does occur under the fatigue stress intensity conditions that have been employed here. Under such specific circumstances, an increase in interfacial strength would be predicted to promote easier (earlier) fibre failure, as is deduced in the current work. *However*, if the composite is tested under lower fatigue stress intensity conditions where fibre failure is unlikely even after ageing, then increased interfacial strength would be expected to be beneficial in promoting crack arrest because the traction forces operating to resist crack opening displacements in its wake will be increased. Further work is required to quantify such mechanisms of crack growth but results to date are in good agreement with these basic concepts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Effects of heat treatment on fibre/matrix interfacial strengths have been measured using a fibre push-out technique. Interfacial strengths have been observed not to change significantly with solution treatment at 910°C, but peak ageing of the matrix increases both the interfacial debonding stress and the frictional stress. Effects of interfacial strength have been seen on the fatigue crack

growth resistance of the peak aged material. Crack growth rates increased and the number of cycles to failure decreased compared with the as-processed and solution treated conditions. Such reduced fatigue crack growth resistance is consistent with an increased incidence of fibre failure in the peak aged material.

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Tables and figures

Ti β 21s / SCS-6 condition	Thickness of fibre / matrix reaction layer / μm
As-processed	0.79
2 hours at 910°C	1.0
6 hours at 910°C	1.3

Table 1. The growth of the fibre/matrix reaction product thickness with exposure at 910°C.

Heat treatment of Ti β 21s/SCS-6 composite	$\tau_{\text{debond}}/\text{MPa}$	standard deviation	$\tau_{\text{friction}}/\text{MPa}$	standard deviation
As-processed	80	9	102	9
2 hours at 910°C	81	12	93	17
6 hours at 910°C	86	6	110	11
8 hours at 540°C	121	9	181	8

Table 2. Interfacial debonding and frictional stresses for the Ti β 21s / SCS-6 composites in the various heat treated conditions.

Heat treatment of Ti β 21s/SCS-6 composite	Number of cycles to failure
As-processed test 1 test 2	1,760,900 grew to crack arrest
2 hours at 910°C	grew to crack arrest
6 hours at 910°C	3,995,187
8 hours at 540°C (PA)	87,900

Table 3. Number of cycles to failure as a function of heat treatment .

Figure 1. A schematic of a load cross-head displacement trace during the fibre push-out operation.

Figure 2. Crack growth resistance curves: da/dN versus total crack length for the as-processed and solution treated Ti B21s / SCS-6 specimens, $R = 0.5$ and $\nu = 10$ Hz. The initial ΔK_{app} is 17 MPa√m in all cases.

Figure 3. Crack growth resistance curves: da/dN versus total crack length for the as-processed and peak aged Ti B21s / SCS-6 specimens, $R = 0.5$ and $\nu = 10$ Hz. The initial ΔK_{app} is 17 MPa√m in all cases.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Fracture surfaces of specimens after failure (a) as-processed material and (b) peak aged material.